

Impedance characteristics of inorganic precipitate membranes

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Abstract : The impedance characteristics of parchment supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and complex lead-copper sulphide inorganic precipitate membranes have been analysed in order to understand the mechanism of ionic diffusion through biomembranes. The electrical resistance (R_x) and capacitance (C_x) have been measured at different electrolyte concentrations and oscillator frequencies.

Impedance values follow the theoretical predictions at high frequency, but at lower frequencies, there is a marked deviation from the ideal behaviour probably due to roughness and non homogeneity of the membrane used in this investigation.

Keywords : Impedance characteristics, membranes, parchment, precipitate.

Introduction

Impedance measurements provide a powerful diagnostic tool for the analysis of many electro-chemical system¹. The behaviour of simple inorganic precipitate membranes and complex inorganic precipitate membranes was studied by various workers^{2,3}.

This paper describes the analysis of membrane impedance of parchment supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and a complex lead-copper sulphide model membranes under various conditions of bathing electrolyte concentration and applied oscillator frequency in order to understand the mechanism of ionic transport through these membranes.

Experimental

Parchment supported lead sulphide and copper sulphide membranes have been prepared by the method of interaction^{4,5}.

The measurements of resistance and capacitance were carried out by making use of mercury to establish electrical contact between membrane surface and a universal LCR bridge 921 without removing the adhering surface liquid. The membranes were equilibrated with a lower concentration of potassium chloride initially than the higher concentration while measuring the resistance and capaci-

tance of the membranes. The effect of oscillator frequency on the resistance and capacitance values have been observed for all the membranes. A platinum wire coated with platinum black dipped in mercury was used as the electrode. The use of long electrode was preferred in order to avoid tip impedance with maintaining temperature at 25 ± 0.1 °C.

Results and discussion

The electrical resistance (R_x) and capacitance (C_x) across parchment supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and complex lead-copper sulphide membranes equilibrated with different concentration of potassium chloride solution at 1 KHz frequency have been measured. The electrical resistance and capacitance were also determined for all three membranes equilibrated with 0.1 M KCl solution by applying different A.C. frequencies. These values are given in Tables 1 and 2.

By using the model equivalent electrical circuit and equations for membrane electrical system⁶ the values of membrane resistance (R_m), capacitance (C_m) and impedance (Z) of the lead sulphide, copper sulphide and complex lead-copper sulphide membranes are calculated, given in Tables 3 and 4. Although the values of R_m and C_m can

Table 1. Electrical resistance (R_x) and capacitance (C_x) observed across parchment-supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and complex lead-copper sulphide membranes equilibrated with different concentrations of potassium chloride at 1 KHz (temp. 25 ± 0.1 °C)

Electrolyte concn. (M/L)	Lead sulphide membrane		Copper sulphide membrane		Complex lead-copper sulphide membrane	
	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)
1×10^{-4}	40.8×10^2	2.4×10^{-2}	26.0×10^2	5.2×10^{-2}	37.5×10^2	3.7×10^{-2}
1×10^{-3}	36.0×10^2	3.6×10^{-2}	18.2×10^2	7.8×10^{-2}	28.7×10^2	5.0×10^{-2}
1×10^{-2}	26.4×10^2	6.0×10^{-2}	11.7×10^2	14.3×10^{-2}	18.1×10^2	8.7×10^{-2}
1×10^{-1}	6.1×10^2	48×10^{-2}	4.2×10^2	91×10^{-2}	10×10^2	37.5×10^{-2}
1×10^0	0.96×10^2	150×10^{-2}	0.61×10^2	156×10^{-2}	1.6×10^2	81.2×10^{-2}
2×10^0	0.72×10^2	240×10^{-2}	0.45×10^2	312×10^{-2}	1.2×10^2	137×10^{-2}

Table 2. Electrical resistance (R_x) and capacitance (C_x) observed across parchment-supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and complex lead-copper sulphide membranes equilibrated with 0.1 M potassium chloride at different oscillator frequencies (temp. 25 ± 0.1 °C)

Oscillator frequency (Hz)	Lead sulphide membrane		Copper sulphide membrane		Complex lead-copper sulphide membrane	
	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)
1×10^3	6.1×10^2	48×10^{-2}	4.2×10^2	91.0×10^{-2}	10×10^2	37.5×10^{-2}
2×10^3	5.0×10^2	36×10^{-2}	3.2×10^2	79.3×10^{-2}	9.5×10^2	31.2×10^{-2}
3×10^3	4.2×10^2	28.8×10^{-2}	2.6×10^2	65.0×10^{-2}	8.8×10^2	26.2×10^{-2}
4×10^3	3.7×10^2	24×10^{-2}	2.1×10^2	61.0×10^{-2}	8.3×10^2	21.2×10^{-2}
5×10^3	3.5×10^2	19.5×10^{-2}	1.8×10^2	56.0×10^{-2}	6.9×10^2	18.2×10^{-2}
6×10^3	3.4×10^2	15.8×10^{-2}	1.7×10^2	50.7×10^{-2}	6.7×10^2	16.0×10^{-2}

be easily computed for simple membranes from bridge readings of R_x and C_x . Such calculations can not be done for complex membrane because it can not be described by definite equivalent electrical circuit. Another equivalent electrical circuit (Fig. 1) has been used to represent the complex membrane in view of uncontrolled simultaneous deposition of lead sulphide and copper sulphide in the interstices of parchment paper⁷. In this case the identity of simple lead sulphide and copper sulphide membranes are lost.

Fig. 1. The equivalent electrical circuit for the complex lead-copper sulphide complex membrane.

It may be concluded that the equivalent electrical circuit may be utilized to represent the behaviour of complex membrane at least in higher concentration ranges. The deviation in dilute concentrations may be assigned to the interfacial polarization and structural changes in the interfacial double layer⁸.

It may therefore be concluded that the membrane/electrolyte system can be represented by a model equivalent electrical circuit⁷ and the values of membrane capacitance (C_m) as a function of electrolyte concentration is accurately predicted by double layer theory. This type of behavior is in agreement with our earlier findings of membrane potential measurements with lead sulphide and copper sulphide membranes as well as in agreement with Tien and Ting⁹ for bilayer membranes that the electrical double layer at the interface control the diffusion process, at least in dilute concentration range¹⁰.

Table 3. Calculated values of membrane resistance (R_m), capacitance (C_m) and impedance (Z) for parchment-supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and a complex lead-copper sulphide membrane equilibrated with different concentrations of potassium chloride at 1 KHz (temp. 25 ± 0.1 °C)

Electrolyte concn.	Lead sulphide membrane			Copper sulphide membrane			Complex lead-copper sulphide membrane		
	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	Z (Ω)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	Z (Ω)	R_x (Ω)	C_x (μ F)	Z (Ω)
1×10^{-4}	148.69×10^2	1.7×10^{-2}	77.89×10^2	62.07×10^2	3.0×10^{-2}	40.17×10^2	86.8×10^2	2.1×10^{-2}	57.08×10^2
1×10^{-3}	90.35×10^2	2.1×10^{-2}	57.03×10^2	41.10×10^2	4.3×10^{-2}	27.35×10^2	64.0×10^2	2.7×10^{-2}	42.87×10^2
1×10^{-2}	53.08×10^2	3.0×10^{-2}	37.43×10^2	22.30×10^2	6.7×10^{-2}	16.15×10^2	36.61×10^2	4.3×10^{-2}	25.74×10^2
1×10^{-1}	7.9×10^2	10.9×10^{-2}	6.94×10^2	4.93×10^2	13.4×10^{-2}	4.55×10^2	11.8×10^2	5.7×10^{-2}	10.86×10^2
1×10^0	2.13×10^2	82.5×10^{-2}	1.43×10^2	2.32×10^2	115×10^{-2}	1.19×10^2	4.0×10^2	48.7×10^{-2}	2.53×10^2
2×10^0	1.33×10^2	110.2×10^{-2}	0.98×10^2	1.03×10^2	175×10^{-2}	0.68×10^2	2.32×10^2	66.4×10^{-2}	1.68×10^2

Table 4. Calculated values of membrane resistance (R_m), capacitance (C_m) and impedance (Z) for parchment-supported lead sulphide, copper sulphide and a complex lead-copper sulphide membrane equilibrated with 0.1 M potassium chloride solution at different oscillator frequencies (temp. 25 ± 0.1 °C)

Oscillator frequency	Lead sulphide membrane			Copper sulphide membrane			Complex lead-copper sulphide membrane		
	R_m (Ω)	C_m (μ F)	Z (Ω)	R_m (Ω)	C_m (μ F)	Z (Ω)	R_m (Ω)	C_m (μ F)	Z (Ω)
1×10^3	7.9×10^2	10.9×10^{-2}	6.94×10^2	4.93×10^2	13.4×10^{-2}	4.55×10^2	11.8×10^2	5.7×10^{-2}	10.86×10^2
2×10^3	5.98×10^2	5.8×10^{-2}	5.47×10^2	3.51×10^2	7.1×10^{-2}	3.35×10^2	10.3×10^2	2.2×10^{-2}	9.89×10^2
3×10^3	5.01×10^2	4.5×10^{-2}	4.59×10^2	2.86×10^2	5.8×10^{-2}	2.72×10^2	9.27×10^2	1.3×10^{-2}	9.03×10^2
4×10^3	4.44×10^2	4.0×10^{-2}	4.05×10^2	2.34×10^2	5.1×10^{-2}	2.24×10^2	8.72×10^2	1.0×10^{-2}	8.51×10^2
5×10^3	4.39×10^2	3.6×10^{-2}	3.92×10^2	1.98×10^2	5.0×10^{-2}	1.89×10^2	7.34×10^2	1.0×10^{-2}	7.12×10^2
6×10^3	4.13×10^2	2.9×10^{-2}	3.75×10^2	1.83×10^2	4.3×10^{-2}	1.78×10^2	7.11×10^2	0.9×10^{-2}	6.9×10^2

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